

NBSINFRA

Empower, Enhance, Protect: NBSINFRA Paving the Way for Resilient Urban Futures

Funded by
the European Union

NBSINFRA is an innovative project funded by the EU, with a primary focus on promoting nature-based solutions (NBS) to protect crucial urban infrastructure against both natural and human-induced hazards.

Our mission extends to creating resilient, and sustainable urban environments capable of withstanding the challenges posed by climate change by collaborative designing, monitoring, and creating through NBS.

NBSINFRA aims to:

Validate NBS
Effectiveness

Innovate Hazard
Response
Methodology

Empower
Communities

Develop a toolkit for
empowerment

Share best practices
EU-wide

Highlight that NBS is
socially acceptable
and affordable

City Labs

NBSINFRA has strategically chosen five diverse European regions to serve as "City Labs" that **will evaluate the cost-effectiveness of NBS in the protection of local infrastructure.**

They aim to maximize impact by **prioritizing solutions that are owned and co-created by residents, end-users, managers, and civil society.**

Fingal
Ireland

Cologne
Germany

Ruse
Bulgaria

Aveiro
Portugal

Prague
Czechia

CITYNATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS INTEGRATION TO LOCAL URBAN INFRASTRUCTURE PROTECTION FOR A CLIMATE RESILIENT SOCIETY

NBSINFRA

Visit our website and get updated with our newsletter and social networks

www.nbsinfra.eu

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